

Study of a Fractional Power Series

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Abstract: In this paper, based on Jumarie type of Riemann-Liouville (R-L) fractional derivative and a new multiplication of fractional power series, we find the exact solution of a fractional power series. In fact, our result is a generalization of traditional calculus result.

Keywords: Jumarie type of R-L fractional derivative, new multiplication, fractional power series, exact solution.

I. INTRODUCTION

Fractional calculus with derivatives and integrals of any real or complex order has its origin in the work of Euler, and even earlier in the work of Leibniz. Shortly after being introduced, the new theory turned out to be very attractive to many famous mathematicians and scientists, for example, Laplace, Riemann, Liouville, Abel, and Fourier. Fractional calculus has important applications in physics, mechanics, biology, electrical engineering, viscoelasticity, control theory, economics, and other fields [1-16].

However, the rule of fractional derivative is not unique, many scholars have given the definitions of fractional derivatives. The common definition is Riemann-Liouville (R-L) fractional derivatives. Other useful definitions include Caputo fractional derivatives, Grunwald-Letnikov (G-L) fractional derivatives, and Jumarie type of R-L fractional derivatives to avoid non-zero fractional derivative of constant function [17-21].

In this paper, we obtain the exact solution of the following α -fractional power series:

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\Gamma(3n\alpha+1)} x^{3n\alpha}, \quad (1)$$

where $0 < \alpha \leq 1$. Jumarie's modified R-L fractional derivative and a new multiplication of fractional power series play important roles in this paper. Moreover, our result is a generalization of the result in ordinary calculus.

II. PRELIMINARIES

At first, we introduce the fractional derivative used in this paper.

Definition 2.1 ([22]): Let $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, and x_0 be a real number. The Jumarie's modified Riemann-Liouville (R-L) α -fractional derivative is defined by

$$({}_{x_0}D_x^\alpha)[f(x)] = \frac{1}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \frac{d}{dx} \int_{x_0}^x \frac{f(t)-f(x_0)}{(x-t)^\alpha} dt, \quad (2)$$

where $\Gamma(\cdot)$ is the gamma function. On the other hand, for any positive integer p , we define $({}_{x_0}D_x^\alpha)^p[f(x)] = ({}_{x_0}D_x^\alpha)({}_{x_0}D_x^\alpha) \cdots ({}_{x_0}D_x^\alpha)[f(x)]$, the p -th order α -fractional derivative of $f(x)$.

Proposition 2.2 ([23]): If α, β, x_0, C are real numbers and $\beta \geq \alpha > 0$, then

$$({}_{x_0}D_x^\alpha)[(x-x_0)^\beta] = \frac{\Gamma(\beta+1)}{\Gamma(\beta-\alpha+1)} (x-x_0)^{\beta-\alpha}, \quad (3)$$

and

$$({}_0D_x^\alpha)[C] = 0. \quad (4)$$

Definition 2.3 ([24]): If x, x_0 , and a_n are real numbers for all n , $x_0 \in (a, b)$, and $0 < \alpha \leq 1$. If the function $f_\alpha: [a, b] \rightarrow R$ can be expressed as $f_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} (x - x_0)^{n\alpha}$ on some open interval containing x_0 , then we say that $f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ is a α -fractional power series at $x = x_0$.

In the following, we introduce a new multiplication of fractional power series.

Definition 2.4 ([25]): If $0 < \alpha \leq 1$. Assume that $f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ and $g_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ are two α -fractional power series at $x = x_0$,

$$f_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} (x - x_0)^{n\alpha}, \quad (5)$$

$$g_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{b_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} (x - x_0)^{n\alpha}. \quad (6)$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned} & f_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha g_\alpha(x^\alpha) \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} (x - x_0)^{n\alpha} \otimes_\alpha \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{b_m}{\Gamma(m\alpha+1)} (x - x_0)^{m\alpha} \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} \left(\sum_{m=0}^n \binom{n}{m} a_{n-m} b_m \right) (x - x_0)^{n\alpha}. \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Equivalently,

$$\begin{aligned} & f_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha g_\alpha(x^\alpha) \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{n!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} (x - x_0)^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha n} \otimes_\alpha \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{b_n}{n!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} (x - x_0)^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha n} \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n!} \left(\sum_{m=0}^n \binom{n}{m} a_{n-m} b_m \right) \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} (x - x_0)^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha n}. \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Definition 2.5 ([26]): If $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, and x is a real number. The α -fractional exponential function is defined by

$$E_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{x^{n\alpha}}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha n}. \quad (9)$$

On the other hand, the α -fractional cosine and sine function are defined as follows:

$$\cos_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n x^{2n\alpha}}{\Gamma(2n\alpha+1)} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{(2n)!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha 2n}, \quad (10)$$

and

$$\sin_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n x^{(2n+1)\alpha}}{\Gamma((2n+1)\alpha+1)} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{(2n+1)!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha (2n+1)}. \quad (11)$$

III. MAIN RESULT

In this section, we obtain the exact solution of a fractional power series.

Example 3.1: Let $0 < \alpha \leq 1$. Find the α -fractional power series

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\Gamma(3n\alpha+1)} x^{3n\alpha}.$$

Solution Let $y_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\Gamma(3n\alpha+1)} x^{3n\alpha}$, then the α -fractional derivatives of $y_\alpha(x^\alpha)$

$$({}_0D_x^\alpha)[y_\alpha(x^\alpha)] = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\Gamma((3n-1)\alpha+1)} x^{(3n-1)\alpha}, \quad (12)$$

$$({}_0D_x^\alpha)^2[y_\alpha(x^\alpha)] = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\Gamma((3n-2)\alpha+1)} x^{(3n-2)\alpha}, \quad (13)$$

Thus,

$$({}_0D_x^\alpha)^2[y_\alpha(x^\alpha)] + ({}_0D_x^\alpha)[y_\alpha(x^\alpha)] + y_\alpha(x^\alpha) = E_\alpha(x^\alpha), \quad (14)$$

and

$$y_\alpha(0) = 1, ({}_0D_x^\alpha)[y_\alpha(x^\alpha)](0) = 0. \quad (15)$$

This is a second order linear α -fractional differential equation, and we can obtain the general solution is

$$y_{\alpha,h}(x^\alpha) = C_1 E_\alpha\left(-\frac{1}{2}x^\alpha\right) \otimes_\alpha \cos_\alpha\left(\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}x^\alpha\right) + C_2 E_\alpha\left(-\frac{1}{2}x^\alpha\right) \otimes_\alpha \sin_\alpha\left(\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}x^\alpha\right), \quad (16)$$

where C_1, C_2 are constants. On the other hand, the particular solution is

$$y_{\alpha,p}(x^\alpha) = \frac{1}{3} E_\alpha(x^\alpha). \quad (17)$$

Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} y_\alpha(x^\alpha) &= y_{\alpha,h}(x^\alpha) + y_{\alpha,p}(x^\alpha) \\ &= C_1 E_\alpha\left(-\frac{1}{2}x^\alpha\right) \otimes_\alpha \cos_\alpha\left(\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}x^\alpha\right) + C_2 E_\alpha\left(-\frac{1}{2}x^\alpha\right) \otimes_\alpha \sin_\alpha\left(\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}x^\alpha\right) + \frac{1}{3} E_\alpha(x^\alpha). \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

By initial value conditions, we have

$$C_1 = \frac{2}{3}, C_2 = 0. \quad (19)$$

That is,

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\Gamma(3n\alpha+1)} x^{3n\alpha} = \frac{2}{3} E_\alpha\left(-\frac{1}{2}x^\alpha\right) \otimes_\alpha \cos_\alpha\left(\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}x^\alpha\right) + \frac{1}{3} E_\alpha(x^\alpha). \quad (20)$$

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, based on Jumarie's modified R-L fractional derivative and a new multiplication of fractional power series, we find the exact solution of a fractional power series. In addition, our result is a generalization of classical calculus result. In the future, we will continue to use Jumarie type of R-L fractional derivative and the new multiplication of fractional power series to solve problems in applied mathematics and fractional differential equations.

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